

Morphologic and Histologic Aberration Potential of Monosodium Glutamate in Male Reproductive Organs of *Mus musculus* (Albino Mice)

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Abstract

Monosodium glutamate (MSG) enhances food flavour, but its safety as additive is still debated across the world. Indiscriminate MSG use in Nigeria is rampant in many local restaurants. This study aimed at investigating morphologic and histologic aberration potential of excessive MSG consumption on male reproductive organs. Three doses were investigated in twenty healthy male mice between 24 – 30 g. The mice were randomly grouped into four groups (n=5), after 10 days acclimatization, groups 1, 2, and 3 were orally administered 100, 200 and 400 mg kg⁻¹ b.w doses, respectively for 6 weeks. Group 4 only received distilled water as control. Animals were fed pellet diet and water *ad libitum* throughout the study and weighed weekly. At expiration of study, animals were sacrificed via jugular puncture. Sperm flushed from epididymis, smear prepared, and testes examined. Dose-dependent increase in weight, histologic aberrations, sperm motility and morphology of treated mice was observed (p<0.05). Histoarchitecture revealed Leydig cell hyperplasia (LCH), distend seminiferous tubules (DST), Hyalinized interstitial tissue (HIT), and scanty sperm in vacuolated seminiferous tubules. Morphologic alteration such as, pin head, banana sperm head, hookless, headless and amorphous sperms were observed in treated mice. This may be attributed to increased doses in MSG suggesting that MSG bound to glutamate receptors causing spermatogenic alterations, oxidative damage, imbalanced gonadotropin and reproductive dysfunction. This study revealed MSG toxicity on spermatozoa and testes. We recommend consumption of fruits and vegetables to mitigate MSG toxicity on reproductive function in human males.

Keywords: Histotoxicity, Monosodium glutamate (MSG), Sperm, Testis,

1.0 Introduction

Ajinomoto is the common name for Monosodium Glutamate (MSG) in Nigeria. MSG is used in most restaurants, eateries, and local food vendors' hives (called Bukataria) to improve and create a unique pleasant taste in food [1]. MSG is commonly sold with trade names such as A-One, Vedan, and Ajinomoto and is usually added as a flavour enhancer to canned food, processed meat, chips, crispy chicken, luncheon and chicken noodles. MSG possess a peculiar taste different from the common sweet, sour, salty, and bitter taste, referred to as "Umami," which endeared it to the choice of food producers [1,2]. Our random survey across local eateries within Lagos state, Nigeria observed that all tribes (Yoruba, Hausa, Igbo etc) utilize MSG for improving the taste of soup, however our interview revealed that the Hausas utilize the highest gramme of MSG / litre

of soup of an average of 500mg/l. Umami is also called "Xien Wei" in Chinese or "savoury, "broth-like" or "meaty taste" in English [2].

T1R1+T1R3, mGluR4, and mGluR1 are three umami receptors that have been scientifically identified, hence, umami was internationally recognized as the fifth basic taste based on biochemical, electrophysiological, and psychophysical studies [3]. Improper labelling of MSG in food additives and ingredients has culminated in high consumption among users [4]. Glutamate has been reported as present naturally in virtually all foods, including breast milk, meat, poultry, fish, and vegetables, with higher levels of free MSG found in vegetables. Glutamate has been described as the most excitatory neurotransmitter in the brain. Studies revealed that around 40% of this neurotransmitter is secreted from the synapses in the central nervous system

and acts through ionotropic (iGluR) and metabotropic (mGluR) glutamate receptors [5]. Therefore, excessive consumption of exogenous glutamate may stimulate increased excitatory effects, culminating in neurotoxicity [6].

Several research studies already reported the numerous health risk of MSG incumbent on humans and rodents. MSG has been implicated as a major cause of 'Chinese restaurant syndrome' characterized by symptoms such as stomach ache, migraine, diarrhoea, chest pain, vomiting and fatigue [7]. Tawfik and AlBadr [8] also reported its neurotoxicity as observed in brain cell damage, epilepsy, degeneration of the retina, stroke and endocrine disorders. MSG reportedly caused asthma [9], obesity [10], oxidative stress in the testis, bone marrow, and red blood cells [11, 12, 13]. Atasevenet al. [14] reported that the exposure of cultured human lymphocytes to 6 concentrations of MSG (250, 500, 2000, 4000, and 8000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) increased the frequency of chromosomal aberrations, sister-chromatid exchanges and micronuclei in a dose-dependent manner. The safety and toxicity of MSG have become highly controversial in recent times due to reports of adverse reactions in people who consumed food containing MSG [15, 16]. This study investigated the toxicologic impression of MSG on the histoarchitecture of the testis and bone marrow of male *Mus musculus* (Albino mice).

2.0 Materials and methods

2.1 Sample Preparation

A pack of MSG (Ajinomoto) was purchased from the popular Oyingbo market in Lagos State. Three dosages of MSG (100mg kg^{-1} , 200mg kg^{-1} , and 400mg kg^{-1}) were freshly prepared in distilled water and stored in sterile bottles until they were ready to be used.

2.2 Experimental Animals

Twenty male mice (*Mus musculus*) weighing between 24-30g were procured from the Nigerian Institute for Medical Research (NIMR) for this experiment and housed at the Botanical Gardens of the Faculty of Science, University of Lagos. They were placed in plastic cages, spread with wood shavings as bedding and acclimatized for two weeks. The cages were kept at room temperature and mice had access to water and

animal pellet feed, *adlibitum*. The animals were then administered the MSG solution orally.

2.3 Ethical approval

The use of albino mice for this project was authorized by the ethical committee of the College of Medicine, University of Lagos (CMULHRECNo. CMUL/ACURECA01/21/803).

2.4 Study Design

The mice were divided into four groups of five animals each. The first three groups were orally administered MSG at 100mg kg^{-1} , 200mg kg^{-1} , and 400mg kg^{-1} respectively while the animals in the 4th group only received distilled water and served as the control. All mice were exposed to treatment for 6 weeks and body weight was recorded weekly, after which they were sacrificed via jugular puncture.

2.5 Sperm Head Assay

The sperm head assay was carried out on the mice after receiving daily treatment for 42 days consecutively according to the protocol described by Oloyede [17]. Male mice were sacrificed, and the epididymis was collected and removed in a petri dish containing physiological saline. Smears were prepared on clean, dry glass slides and stained with a 9:1 mixture of normal saline and Eosin Y dye for 45 minutes. The slides were air-dried before being examined for abnormalities under a binocular microscope at x1000 magnification.

2.6 Sperm Motility and Count Assay

Sperm motility and count assay was done according to Kadir et al. [18]. A drop of semen was placed on a glass slide to, 2.9% sodium citrate was added. This slide was then covered with a glass slip, the microscopic fields were viewed under the light microscope to determine the motile and non-motile spermatozoa. Haemocytometer was used for sperm count. The cauda epididymis was minced in normal saline, then filtered and an aliquot of 10 μl was placed on the hemocytometer. The improved Neubauer chamber (Deep 1/10m, LABART, Munich, Germany) was used for the count, under a light microscope

2.7 Histology

Testes were prepared using the microtome RM 2235 and stained with H and E (Hematoxylin and

Eosin) for histologic analysis using a binocular light microscope.

2.8 Statistical Analysis

The data were subjected to a sample T-Test to determine the statistical significance of the difference between the two means of various parameters between the control and experimental groups. To get the P-value, a t-test in Microsoft Excel was utilized. A significant level of less than 0.05 was defined and considered significant.

3.0 Results

Table 1: Body weight of mice during exposure to MSG for 42 days

Treatment	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5	Week 6
Control	25.72±0.47	25.0±0.65	26.32±1.11	27.48±0.72	25.76±1.87	26.56±1.51
100 mg kg ⁻¹	27.7±0.75	26.48±3.92	30.04±2.04	30.92±1.99	31.24±0.72 ^b	32.73±0.65 ^b
200 mg kg ⁻¹	29.68±0.58 ^a	29.78±0.7 ^a	30.9±0.54 ^b	32.14±0.98 ^b	37.09±0.61 ^c	33.34±0.63 ^b
400 mg kg ⁻¹	31.08±0.52	32.18±1.51	31.49±0.56	32.34±0.69	34.02±0.44 ^b	35.42±0.55 ^b

Values were presented as mean ± SEM. Where n=5, value a = p<0.05 significant, b=p<0.01 very significant, c=p<0.001 highly significant.

3.1 Sperm motility

Sperm motility reduced significantly in a dose-dependent manner from 100 mg kg⁻¹ to 400 mg kg⁻¹. Motility was almost 300% higher in the control than the highest frequency of motility in the treatment groups.

Table 2: Sperm motility count after exposure of mice to MSG for 42 days

Treatment	Sperm motility
Control (Distl. Water)	2940.00±240.00
100 mg kg ⁻¹	1065.00±485.00 ^b
200 mg kg ⁻¹	1045.00±495.00 ^b
400 mg kg ⁻¹	880.00±100.00 ^c

Values are presented as mean ± SEM. Where n=5, value a = p<0.05 significant, b=p<0.01 very significant, c=p<0.001 highly significant.

3.2 Histology

Fig 1 (A-H): micrograph showing the testicular histologic section of mice of control and MSG-treated groups (100–400 mg kg⁻¹). Testicular tissues of the control (Fig. A) showed normal histoarchitecture, indicating conserved spermatozoa (S), seminiferous tubules (ST), and intact myofibroblast (MF). Figures 1B and 1C showed disorganized germinal epithelium (DGE) exposing the spermatids. Fig. 1D and 1E treated

with 200 mg kg⁻¹ MSG had significant alterations such as, Leydig cell hyperplasia (LCH), distend seminiferous tubules (DST), and Hyalinized interstitial tissue (HIT). The 400 mg kg⁻¹ MSG treated mice (Fig 1F, G, and H) showed severe alterations such as scanty sperm in vacuolated seminiferous tubule (V), DGE, LCH, DST, and vacuolated seminiferous tubule (V).

3.3 Sperm Morphology

Fig 2A. Showed Normal sperm (NS) with hook in control. B; 100 mg kg⁻¹ showed Pin head (PH) and Banana head sperms (BHS). C; 200 mg kg⁻¹ revealed Headless (HD) and Amorphous sperm (AM), while the 400 mg kg⁻¹ consisted of sperms with retarded Hook (H).

4.0 Discussion

Despite the global acceptance of MSG as an ingredient that enhances the flavor of processed food and homemade meals, there is still an ongoing debate about its safety as a food additive [19]. In the present study, we investigated the morphologic and histologic effects of three doses of MSG in male mice models by assessing sperm motility, sperm head morphology, and testes histology.

The increasing growth rate observed (table 1) across all treatment groups suggests that consuming MSG contributes to weight gain, which could, in turn, lead to obesity and other cardiovascular diseases, as well as infertility. The dose-dependent increase in weight of MSG-exposed mice corroborates with the results of several *in vivo* studies [20, 21]. There is an unclear link between taste perception threshold of different tastes (sweet, bitter, sour, salt, and umami) and body weight, moreover, obese women were reported to have higher MSG (umami) taste perception [22]. Thus, the dose-

dependent increase in mice weight observed in this study could be due to an increased umami taste perception by the mice.

Since diet has been implicated as a major factor that contributes to the high prevalence (30-50%) of male infertility cases globally [23], only male Swiss mice were used to assess the morphologic and histologic effect of MSG in this study. To date, there is a paucity of available information on the effect of MSG consumption on human reproductive function, which makes Swiss mice (*Mus musculus*) suitable models for biomedical research studies because approximately 95% of their genes are shared with humans and data from mice studies could be extrapolated to humans [24]. This study showed a decline in the motility of sperm cells in a dose-dependent manner from 100 mg kg⁻¹ to 400 mg kg⁻¹ whereas the control group showed about 300% higher sperm motility (table 2). Contrary to the normal histoarchitecture observed in the control group, MSG-treated mice showed histologic alterations such as disorganized germinal epithelium (in the 100 mg kg⁻¹ group), Leydig cell hyperplasia (LCH), distend seminiferous tubules (DST), and Hyalinized interstitial tissue (HIT) (in the 200 mg kg⁻¹ group), as well as scanty sperm in vacuolated seminiferous tubules, DST, HIT and LCH histological alterations in the 400 mg kg⁻¹ group. Distorted sperm morphology such as banana sperm head, pin head, headless and amorphous sperm observed in this study are also in consonance with some earlier reports on the toxicologic effects of MSG on the testes such as alteration in sperm morphology, oligospermia, haemorrhage of the testes and decreased sperm cells thereby resulting in male infertility [20, 21]. These irregularities may be attributed to the inhibitory effects of MSG on prostaglandin synthesis [25], and deterioration of the cells of seminiferous tubules [26]. MSG may have targeted the glutamate transporter and receptors on the epithelium of the seminiferous tubules cells [21]. It may also be due the effect of the MSG neurotoxin on the physiological activities of the hypothalamus-pituitary-gonadal system [27, 28]. Moreover, the neurogenic anomalies observed in MSG-treated mice has been reported to significantly affect the hormonal levels of testosterone, follicle stimulating hormone (FSH)

and Leutenizing hormone (LH) [21] that are very vital for the normal function of the testis and stimulation of healthy spermatogenesis. These suggest that increased MSG has the capacity to bind to glutamate receptors whose interaction consequently leads to spermatogenic and histological alterations, oxidative damage, imbalance of gonadotropin hormone and eventually reproductive dysfunction [24].

5.0 Conclusion

This study has revealed that increased MSG in food has the capacity to induce significant damage to the testicular architecture and cause major alteration in reproductive hormone secretion which may lead to adverse effect in male reproductive system, consequently culminating in male infertility. Therefore, we highly recommend the inclusion of very minimal amounts of MSG in food as well as the consumption of food rich in fruits and vegetables to mitigate the effect of MSG on reproductive function in human males. Alternatively, vitamin supplements could be taken to ameliorate the effect of ingested MSG on reproductive health.

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